

Characterization of Longitudinal Patterns in the Daytime Ionosphere with ICON EUV Airglow

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ABSTRACT

The NASA Ionospheric Connection Explorer Extreme Ultraviolet spectrograph, ICON EUV, images one-dimensional altitude profiles of the daytime EUV airglow between 54-88 nm. This spectral range contains several OII emission features derived from the photoionization of atomic oxygen by solar EUV. The primary target of the ICON EUV is the bright OII (⁴P – ⁴S) triplet emission at 83.4 nm that is used in combination with a dimmer but complementary feature (²P – ²D) at 61.7 nm that are jointly analyzed to determine the best-fit solution of ionospheric O⁺ density profile between 150-450 km. From this result, the daytime ionospheric F-region peak electron density and height, NmF2 and HmF2 respectively, are inferred. The low-inclination orbit allows measurements across all local times, but also has a precession rate such that low and equatorial latitudes are sampled at all times over a 48-day period. This paper presents observations of the global patterns in ionospheric HmF2 and NmF2 obtained from the first two years of ICON EUV measurements, which occurred during solar minimum conditions, specifically examining longitudinal patterns in these parameters in a fixed local time frame with respect to the persistent longitudinal wave-4 features created by waves in the lower atmosphere.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Ionospheric Connection Explorer (ICON) is a NASA mission that was launched in October 2019 to answer long-standing, fundamental questions about how the ionosphere responds to energy and momentum drivers in the troposphere and stratosphere below [Immel, *et al.*, 2018]. ICON was placed into an approximately circular, 27-degree inclination orbit near 600 km altitude. Although the ICON mission accomplished its main science objectives over its more than three years of operations, the spacecraft experienced an apparent loss of communication in November 2022 that ended the data collection efforts. One of the sensors on the ICON payload is the Extreme UltraViolet (EUV) spectrograph that images altitude profiles of airglow across the spectral range 55-89 nm [Sirk *et al.*, 2017]. The main measurement targets of the ICON EUV are emission features near 83.4 and 61.7 nm that are used to determine the altitude profile of O⁺, from which the characteristic ionospheric F2 plasma density peak (NmF2) and height (HmF2) are inferred [Stephan, 2016; Stephan *et al.*, 2017]. The ICON EUV products were validated against a significant

number of ground-based ionosonde and COSMIC GPS radio occultation measurements to confirm the overall accuracy of the HmF2 values, and the precision of the NmF2 products needed to address the ICON examination of variation in these values [Wautelet *et al.*, 2022]. The systematic 50-60% offset in NmF2 that was found in this comparison is under examination as part of an ongoing comprehensive review of systematic uncertainties in both sensor calibration and airglow modeling assumptions – a known constraint of this remote sensing methodology is that the absolute accuracy of NmF2 is highly sensitive to small systematic errors such that this observed magnitude of systematic offset in NmF2 can be accounted for by only a 10-15% systematic error in the measured radiances. Nevertheless, the ICON EUV has produced ionospheric profiles that can be used to assess the morphology and relative changes in the daytime ionosphere relevant to the original ICON mission science objectives. This work summarizes a review of the longitudinal and latitudinal characteristics of NmF2 and HmF2, specifically presenting summary maps of these parameters over one full sampling cycle of all local times (approximately 48 days) around January 2020 and June 2020. These summary maps provide a new global view of wave-4 phenomenology specifically in O⁺ in the daytime ionosphere as derived from EUV remote sensing.

2. OBSERVATIONS

The ICON EUV integrates over every 12-second interval to collect a one-dimensional altitude profile of spectral features binned into 12 distinct spectral bands corresponding to different emission lines in the terrestrial atmosphere and plasmasphere. Most of the emissions are generated by ionospheric O⁺, although other bright emissions of helium at 58.4 nm and some nitrogen ion emissions are also observed. Because of the low inclination of the ICON orbit and the orientation of the ICON EUV to view to the port side of the spacecraft, the measurements are made predominantly toward the northern hemisphere with occasional spacecraft maneuvers allowing some measurements of magnetically conjugate regions toward the southern hemisphere. Additionally, the ICON EUV does not collect data while the spacecraft is located in the South Atlantic Anomaly (SAA) due to the damaging impacts of high-energy particles on the detector. Figure 1 shows the relatively uniform cadence and global coverage of measurements, here geolocated to the location where the tangent point line of sight is at 300 km. While this image is compiled over a year of operations, it is similar to what is achieved over an orbital precession cycle that samples all local times in each region of the globe covered by the orbit/measurement track over period of about 48 days. Some orbits have segments used for routine spacecraft operations in support of the other ICON sensors that limit the ICON EUV measurements in these spans, as visible in this figure over the Pacific Ocean near 135W longitude.

For this analysis, we have used version 3 (v03) of the ICON EUV Level 2 data. We have filtered out specific ICON EUV Level 2 data that generated a level-2 warning flag (generally this occurs for a high chi-square value of the fit, although other factors in the data quality are evaluated as such). We have aggregated these data into global maps of HmF2 and NmF2 over one orbit precession cycle representing the two solstice extremes (day of year 1-48, labeled as January and day of year 185-233 labeled as June) condition for year 2020. It is noteworthy that this is during the crux of solar minimum, with F10.7 between 65-75 sfu, although the solar flux is rising during this time.

Each set of images is generated in 2-hour intervals in local time (LT), starting at 09-11 LT through to 15-17 LT. In each map that is presented, we have aggregated the data and calculated the mean value for HmF2 and NmF2 in each of 72 longitude bins over the global 360-degree range (5-degree resolution) and 45 latitude bins restricted to 30S to 60N degrees (2-degree resolution), noting that some of the northern and southern latitude regions do not contain any data points as shown in Figure 1. We have confirmed the uniform sampling of these points by evaluation of emission features that are unaffected by ionospheric species, including the 61.7 nm emission that is used in the analysis to specify thermospheric and solar conditions of the modeled 83.4 nm emission, the prime determinant of the plasma density distribution.

Figure 1. Sampling map for the ICON EUV over one year, at the geolocation where the line of sight tangent altitude is 300 km. The satellite itself is in a 28-degree inclination and approximately 17 degrees south of each measurement. The sensor high voltage is turned off when the satellite is located in a region around the SAA.

The ICON sensor suite also includes an Ion Velocity Meter (IVM) that is designed to collect, among its data products, in situ plasma density measurements [Heelis, et al., 2017]. For each of the mapping of HmF2 and NmF2 obtained for the ICON EUV, we have provided a comparable average value for plasma density obtained at the spacecraft altitude near 600 km.

3. RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the first of these map sets, corresponding to 09-11 LT. In the January time period, HmF2 derived from the EUV measurements shows the highest values peaking near 330-370 km, located near to and slightly south of the geomagnetic equator. A mildly apparent periodicity consistent with the wave-4 signature, interrupted by the SAA blackout for the ICON EUV, is visible in the data. NmF2 for this time shows the highest values near the 20N magnetic latitude position, but with less of an obvious wave-4 signature, particularly in the region 45E-90E longitude. In the July time period, the patterns in HmF2 are more scattered, while NmF2 shows clear wave-4 signatures located near the magnetic equator. During both of these periods, the IVM data show very low densities with faint apparitions of a wave-4 signature consistent with the ICON EUV results, but offset in position due to the differences in the geolocation of these in situ measurements versus the airglow remote sensing data.

Figure 3 shows similar data but for the next time local block, 11-13 LT. Here the January solstice period shows an increase in HmF2, nearing 400 km at the highest, but with similar patterning as seen at the earlier local time. The higher NmF2 values for this period are still located near 20N magnetic latitude but now much more narrowly confined near this location and still without significant patterning. IVM is now showing higher densities and a clear wave-r pattern with similarities to the ICON EUV HmF2 pattern, although perhaps slightly shifted in longitude. For the June time period, HmF2 is now more distinctly formed and manifesting stronger wave-4 signatures. NmF2 is likewise beginning to show similar patterns in the locations of the highest densities, particularly in the region near 90E longitude. This region is also the location of the highest IVM densities, although less dense peaks are present at all longitudes matching the ICON EUV HmF2 and NmF2 maps.

Figure 4 shows the third local time segment, 13-15 LT. Here the wave-4 feature can be seen in HmF2 in both the January and June time periods, shifted in latitude to match the subsolar position for each solstice season. NmF2, in contrast, now shows clear peaks at the 20N magnetic equator location as well as contrasting pattern of higher densities nearer to the equator in regions where HmF2 is lower. IVM shows perhaps its highest densities as well as the strongest wave-4 signature at the equator that pairs with the

locations where the ICON EUV HmF2 peaks are located, near the magnetic equator, with the exception of the location between 45E-90E longitude.

Figure 5 shows the last time period 15-17 LT. Here the HmF2 values shows the complete wave-4 phenomenology, with the peak in the region between 45E-90E longitude now manifesting back near the magnetic equator in line with the IVM morphology. The corresponding high-density NmF2 value is absent here, although the wave-4 structure in this parameter is no longer as visible at these later local times.

Figure 2. ICON data collected in the local time band of 09-11 LT. The top and middle panels show averaged from measurements of the ICON EUV. The bottom panel shows the ICON IVM in situ plasma density measurements. January data are collected between day of year 1-48. June data are collected between day of year 185-233. See text for additional details.

Figure 3. Same as Figure 2 but for 11-13 LT.

Figure 4. Same as Figure 2 but for 13-15 LT.

Figure 5. Same as Figure 2 but for 15-17 LT.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The longitude-latitude-LT morphology of the daytime ionosphere morphology seen in the ICON EUV measurements is consistent with and explained by the now well-known combination of solar ionization, vertical uplift of the equatorial plasma fountain, and longitudinal wave-4 patterning generated by tidal waves in the lower atmosphere during solar minimum (e.g *Kil et al.*, 2008). The north-south location of HmF2 peaks shift with season, but are generally located near the magnetic equator where uplift also generates higher plasma densities at the spacecraft altitude where they are measured by the in situ IVM sensor. As the plasma fountain evolves during the day, plasma motion down the field line creates higher peaks in density at the crests of the equatorial ionization anomaly, with additional dynamical forces moving plasma and blurring some of the wave-4 phenomenology.

The remote sensing methodology of the ICON EUV has some limitations in that it is sensitive to O⁺, such that it is increasingly insensitive to ionospheres with HmF2 below about 235 km, or to particularly low-density ionosphere. However, the preponderance of these data are in the early morning (before 09 LT) which were not evaluated as part of this study, and the highest latitudes that are beyond the reach of the equatorial ionization anomaly that is of interest here.

While the wave-4 patterns have been observed in the daytime using radiative recombination emissions (e.g. Kil *et al.*, 2013), those observations were not directly connected to either HmF2 or NmF2 but rather represent a measurement between 420-500 km where the emission is distinguishable from the thermospheric dayglow. These data were also compared to in situ data on ROCSAT-1 at 600 km – akin to what IVM collects for ICON. Measurements of HmF2 from radio occultation data collected by the COSMIC and COSMIC 2 satellites (e.g. Liu *et al.*, 2010, 2021) have shown the equatorial location and longitudinal patterns similar to what is presented here. This work also demonstrates the persistent presence of patterns in O⁺ identified by England *et al.* (2019) over day of year 75-95 in 2020 as part of a more comprehensive analysis of six months of densities, winds, and temperatures measured by the ICON mission.

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